

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE THEORY OF NEO-OTTOMANISM IN TURKISH MILITARY POLICY

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ABSTRACT

The transformations in the foreign policy doctrine of the Republic of Turkey are analyzed on the example of Turkish-Iraqi relations, which have intensified in recent years. The author proves that the conceptual basis of innovations in Ankara's foreign policy course is based on two modern concepts that are liberal in nature: neo-Ottomanism, theorized in Turkey, appealing to the unity of peoples who were once part of the Ottoman Empire, and transnationalism, conceptualized in the United States, aimed at strengthening non-governmental relations between states. The article emphasizes that the "Greater Middle East Initiative" program developed by Western political scientists was supposed to strengthen the position of the Republic of Turkey as a regional power. Ankara's new course and the Turkish-Iraqi relations of recent years indicate that Turkey is able to neutralize the Kurdish threat, increase the importance of relations with Baghdad, as well as normalize relations with Moscow.

The idea of reestablishing the Near and Middle East, stretching from the kingdom of Morocco in the West to the Kazakh steppes in the East, as is known, was framed within the walls of American research centers and universities at the turn of the millennium. Later, on the eve of the opening of the NATO summit in Istanbul in 2004, the official name of the project, which sounded in English as "Greater Middle East Initiative", which roughly translated into Russian meant "Greater Middle East Initiative", was changed to «The extended Middle East and North Africa Initiative». The new name in Russian already sounded like the "Expanded Middle East and North Africa Initiative". According to the official version voiced in the United States, this project was based on the ideas of democratizing the socio-political life of the peoples of the Middle East and North African regions, ensuring the protection of human rights and property, carrying out liberal reforms in the economy and justice. According to the researchers, in total, the program of transformation of the eastern world from the republics of the former USSR included all three states of Transcaucasia and five countries of Central Asia. According to the ideologists of the color revolutions, one of the most important roles was

assigned to Turkey. It was assumed that Ankara would be a kind of example of conflict-free modernization of Eastern society for countries with predominantly Muslim and Turkic-speaking populations. As you know, the start of this program was given in December 2010. in Tunisia, when the self-immolation of a fruit seller in the central city square gave rise to popular unrest, which later acquired a chain character.

Simultaneously with the development of a project to reform the Middle East by American specialists in Turkey, the question of the role that, as seen in Ankara, this country will play in the implementation of the plans of overseas allies was actualized. In general, the political elite of the country understood that American-Turkish allied relations and Washington's active policy in the region would allow Turkey to strengthen its position in the Middle East. The question was only tactical nuances, how competently and consistently Ankara should act.

One of the areas that, according to the plan of the reformers of the Middle East, should have been given special attention was the Turkish-Iraqi relations that almost came to naught in the 80s and 90s of the last century. Both political, economic and cultural contacts between Ankara and Baghdad were subject to resuscitation. I note that initially the entourage of Turkish Prime Minister T. Erdogan was rather skeptical about the prospect of resuming contacts with a neighboring state, seeing in the Iraqi Kurds a potential threat to the integrity of Turkish statehood. However, towards the end of the noughties, as Professor of international Law A. Davutoglu, a theorist of the so-called foreign-political neo-Ottomanism, and his associates strengthened their positions in the political elite of Turkey, doubts about the need for cooperation with Baghdad began to dissipate rapidly.

In February 2008, a document entitled "On relations with Iraq" was approved at a meeting of the National Security Secretariat of the Republic of Turkey. For the first time in the history of Turkey, a state body that ensures the national security of the country has declared the importance of developing Turkish-Iraqi interstate relations. Shortly after that, the adviser to Prime Minister A. Davutoglu, who will become the country's foreign minister in a year, went to Baghdad to meet with Iraqi President D. Talabani and Prime Minister N. Al-Maliki. It is noteworthy that during the visit of the Turkish official to the neighboring country, he also met with the Prime Minister of the regional government of Iraqi Kurdistan, N. Barzani. The main idea that was periodically voiced during Davutoglu's visit was that Ankara is ready for a radical revision of relations with Baghdad. On the same days, negotiations were held in the Turkish capital between Iraqi Vice President T. Hashimi and T. Erdogan, which ended with "the inclusion of Turkish business in the list of companies that will explore hydrocarbon reserves in northern Iraq".

And already in March 2008, D. Talabani paid an official visit to Ankara, where the Iraqi leader proposed to the Turkish side to form a separate state structure overseeing the entire spectrum of interstate relations. In addition, the Iraqi President expressed a desire to invite Turkish business to the construction of the new Iraqi-Turkish oil pipeline Kirkuk-Ceyhan.

On July 10, 2008, T. Erdogan's visit to Baghdad took place, which, according to experts, became a turning point in relations between the two states. During the visit of the Turkish Prime Minister, an agreement was reached on the establishment of a Strategic Turkish-Iraqi Council, the work of which should be carried out with the support of the governments of both

states. Agreements were signed on combating terrorism and cooperation in the military sphere, the last of which provided for the interaction of the heads of the headquarters of the armed forces of Turkey and Iraq. In March 2009, for the first time after a thirty-three-year break, a Turkish president paid an official visit to Iraq. A. Gul's meeting with the leadership of the Kurdish autonomy of Iraq was marked by the fact that the highest person in Turkey declared recognition of Kurdish statehood. So, the Turkish president, instead of the usual "leadership of the autonomy of Northern Iraq", for the first time pronounced "leadership of the regional Kurdish autonomy". A. Gul's words about the brotherhood of the Turkish and Kurdish peoples clearly showed Ankara's desire to "reset" its policy in relation to Northern Iraq. In a short time, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Turkey opened diplomatic missions in various cities of Iraq. For example, in April 2009 the consulate in Basra started functioning, in January 2010 – in Erbil.

Economic cooperation between the two countries is also gaining momentum at a pace never seen before. The most significant jump in trade occurred in 2009. So, if in the first two months of 2008 the import of Turkish goods from a neighboring country amounted to approximately 472 million US dollars, then in January and February of the following year this figure reached the level of 830 million dollars. As you can see, the import growth was almost 76%. Turkey, as a rule, imports consumer goods to Iraq: household appliances, food, textiles, non-ferrous metals and steel, furniture and building materials. Turkish imports from Iraq consist mainly of oil and refined products. It should be noted that before T. Erdogan's team came to power in Turkey, the shares of imports and exports in Turkish-Iraqi trade were about the same. However, due to the fact that the Erdogan administration has taken a course to develop exports in the country's foreign trade, in the last few years, Iraqi exports to Turkey account for only a fifth of imports. The volume of Turkish imports in 2012 amounted to 10.8 billion US dollars, which is 2.7 times more than in 2008. The importance of the Iraqi market for Turkish entrepreneurs is quite eloquently demonstrated by the fact that the customs located on the Turkish-Iraqi border passes as many trucks per day as all the other fourteen points on other borders combined. In other words, thanks to the growth of foreign trade turnover between the two countries in recent years, the economies of Iraq and Turkey have grown together into a single economic system. Turkish entrepreneurs are also actively involved in the development of retail trade in Iraq. In Erbil, Mosul, Kirkuk, Baghdad, the number of Turkish shopping malls has increased significantly in recent years. The banking sector also received an impetus in its development. As you know, Turkish legislation strictly regulates foreign exchange transactions in international trade: entrepreneurs- residents of Turkey are prohibited from keeping money in foreign currency in foreign banks. This circumstance prompted Turkish banks to open their branches in various cities of Iraq. The growth of trade turnover between the two countries is also accompanied by an increase in transportation. After a seventeen-year break, on October 26, 2008, the national Turkish air carrier, Turkish Airlines, resumed its flights to Iraq. In addition to this company, a private Turkish airline, Atlas Jet, began operating flights to Iraqi cities from Istanbul and Ankara. Bus transport carriers have also stepped up their activities in the Iraqi direction.

Cultural ties between the two countries have developed, as a rule, thanks to the initiatives of Turkish entrepreneurs working in Iraq. Some projects have been supported by

the Turkish government, first of all, it concerns activities in the field of education and student exchange. For example, the Fezalar educational courses that had been functioning in Iraq for more than fourteen years, which were also founded by Turkish entrepreneurs, were transformed into lyceums in the noughties. The total number of these lyceums, called "Ishik", which means "light" in Turkish, has reached ten. In 2008, with the support of the Turkish government, the Turkish-Iraqi University was founded in Erbil, the first higher education institution in Iraq funded by Ankara. Interestingly, obtaining secondary and higher education in Turkish educational institutions in Iraq is considered quite prestigious. Ankara is also pursuing an active policy in the neighboring country in promoting the Turkish language. Quite a lot - an important factor for this is that in the northern part of Iraq there is a large Turkic-speaking population - Turkomans. In the noughties, the Department of Turkish Philology at the Faculty of Foreign Languages was opened at the largest higher educational institution in Iraqi Kurdistan - Selahaddin University.

Simultaneously with the transformations that took place in the sphere of Turkish-Iraqi relations, the geopolitical landscape of the Middle East was radically changing. The fact is that the Kurdish question has become louder and more insistent in the region, threatening the territorial integrity of four neighboring states - Turkey, Iraq, Iran and Syria. It must be admitted that Ankara is clearly aware that Washington stands behind the Kurdish politicians who have become more active over the past decade with their interests in the Middle East. "Even if the issue of creating an independent Kurdish state has not yet matured, activities in the region aimed at creating a powerful autonomous Kurdistan in northern Iraq are in full swing. The US plans include the formation of a federal form of statehood in Iraq with the subsequent collapse of the country, as signals of such developments are often received. Washington, supporting the Kurds in the north of the country, uses the Kurdish factor to prevent the rapprochement of Iraqi Shiites with Iran".

Indeed, the events that began in the region after the military operation "Desert Storm", carried out in 1991, and continue to the present, are developing in the interests of the Kurdish population. Modern Turkey also played a significant role in this, which, under moderate Islamists, refused to openly support the Turkomans of Northern Iraq, as a result of which the Turkic factor in the internal political alignment of Iraqi forces ceased to play its former role. Erdogan, distancing himself from the principle of ethnocentrism in domestic and foreign policy, which, as will be said below, is characteristic of the Islamic political tradition, contributed to the formation of a powerful Kurdish political movement in Iraq. Moreover, Ankara provides serious economic support to Iraqi Kurdistan. However, it is necessary to admit this, economic cooperation between Iraqi Kurdistan and Turkey is based mainly on the extraction and transportation of hydrocarbons. Thus, even before the formation of a moderate Islamist government in Turkey in 1996, The Kirkuk-Ceyhan oil pipeline has resumed its operation. Let me remind you that it consists of two branches, the first of which was built in 1977, and the second in 1987. After Iraq's aggression against Kuwait in 1990, oil pumping on both branches was suspended. In addition to oil, Turkey is interested in supplying Iraqi natural gas to the country. A private "Turkish Energy Company" established in early 2013 with the support of the government in March 2013. signed an agreement with the authorities of the Kurdish autonomy on the development of gas fields in the territory of Iraqi Kurdistan

and the construction of a gas pipeline. Gas transportation is expected to begin in 2017. It is noteworthy that the government in Ankara, in order to avoid criticism from the official Baghdad, did not sign the text of the agreement, transferring these functions to a private company. Simultaneously with the development of a new gas pipeline, according to experts, work is underway to lay another oil pipeline.

It is noteworthy that economic cooperation between Turkey and Iraqi Kurdistan has become a serious irritant for the central government of Iraq. The Iraqi Government has been attacking the Turkish leadership with a wave of criticism for several years. Ankara is periodically accused of undermining the territorial integrity of Iraq, inciting Iraqi Kurdistan to further tougher actions in defending its rights and freedoms. The Prime Minister of Iraq, N. N., who resigned in August 2014. Al-Maliki has repeatedly stated that Turkey and Turkish entrepreneurs cannot sign trade and other commercial agreements with the Kurdish authorities in the north of the country without the consent of the central Iraqi government. Almaliki called all agreements between the Turks and the Iraqi Kurds, including in the field of extraction, processing and transportation of energy carriers, contrary to the Constitution of Iraq. According to experts, the activity of Turkish business circles in Northern Iraq is pushing the central government towards rapprochement with Iran and Syria. For example, pro-government political circles in Iraq have harshly criticized Ankara for its interference in the internal affairs of Syria. So, the events that unfolded in the sphere of Turkish-Iraqi relations at the end of the noughties and at the beginning of the second decade demonstrate that the rapprochement of Ankara and Baghdad across the entire spectrum of interstate relations has acquired special importance in the eyes of the leadership of both states. Moreover, as paradoxical as it sounds, Turkish-Kurdish cooperation, criticized by the central Iraqi authorities, has also received a powerful impetus in its development. The theoretical justification for such an ambivalent policy of Ankara towards a neighboring state, as many Turkish experts believe, lies in the adoption by the Cabinet of T. Erdogan of a new concept for the Middle East of building intergovernmental relations, which is based on the principles of neo-Ottomanism and transnationalism.

Neo-Ottomanism is a rather complex and ambiguously perceived concept in the scientific community, appealing to the brilliant past of the Ottoman Turks. Neo-Ottomanism is by its nature multifaceted. In addition to purely political components, it includes elements of the cultural life of the Ottoman society, economic and legal issues. In the foreign policy context, neo-Ottomanism implies a Turkish-centrist vector of development of the Middle East region, which, as is known, has been dominated by Istanbul for several centuries. However, the authorship of neo-Ottomanism in its foreign policy understanding does not belong to the associates of T. Erdogan. For the first time, neo-Ottomanism was talked about during the presidency of T. Ozal, who, as is known, was considered an admirer of the foreign policy concepts of R. Reagan and M. Thatcher, developed within the framework of neoliberalism. Recall that the vision of international affairs from Washington and London in the 80s of the last century was strikingly different from the relatively peaceful foreign policy doctrine of these countries of previous decades. The Falklands War of the British Crown, the aggressive rhetoric of the administration of R. T. Ozal, being an ardent Americanophile, made the most of the innovative ideas of the neoliberal Atlantists at the regional level, starting a stormy activity

in the post-Soviet Turkic-speaking states in the early 90s. Moderate Islamists of modern Turkey largely adopted those basic provisions that were developed by theorists from T. Ozal's entourage, adopting them to the Islamic and Middle Eastern discourse, which, however, made its own significant adjustments. For example, the ideas of Turkism in the neo-Ottomanism of moderate Islamists were significantly weakened, which was favorably received by Moscow. Indeed, the key point in the concept of neo-Ottomanism of A. Davutoglu was the rejection of the element of ethnicity. This is explained by the fact that the Islamic legal tradition categorically does not accept this factor in the construction of statehood and in the conceptualization of foreign policy doctrine. The second important difference between the "new" neo-Ottomanism is the fact that their concept is aimed at pursuing a course, albeit relatively, but still independent of Washington. For example, the embarrassment caused by the fact that on March 1, 2003, the Turkish parliament refused to grant the country's territory to the Western allies as a springboard for the invasion of Iraq was widely covered in the Russian press. Acting within the framework of neo-Ottomanism of moderate Islamists, in August 2008, during the so-called action of the need for peace conducted by Moscow in relation to Tbilisi, Turkish parliamentarians, appealing to the provisions of the Montreux Convention of 1936, banned the passage of American military vessels into the Black Sea. There are many similar examples.

The concept of transnationalism, developed by modern American political scientists, largely echoes the neo-Ottomanism of A. Davutoglu. Supporters of transnationalism adhere to liberal views, the most radical of them are ideologically close to libertarians. In the theory of international relations, the liberal approach, as is known, was developed in the XVIII–XIX centuries. In modern conditions, the influence of liberal ideas is no less noticeable. In contrast to realism, the theorists of modern liberalism do not consider the institution of the state as the most important actor in the international arena. Among the actors determining the foreign policy course of a particular state, modern liberals include a person, non-governmental organizations, international corporations, etc. Moreover, as is known, modern liberalism, questioning the viability of the so-called Westphalian approach to interstate relations, distances itself as much as possible from the institution of the state. The model of transnational relations has received quite a lot of recognition in the academic environment. Often this model is called transnationalism, which is based on the following basic postulates. Firstly, modern interstate relations are much broader and more multifaceted than they were a few decades ago. Moreover, the place of intergovernmental contacts in this spectrum of international relations is gradually narrowing. Secondly, with an unprecedented increase in the number of participants in international relations, the scope of cooperation is also expanding. So, if initially interstate relations were directly or indirectly related to issues of war and peace, at present the complex of issues regulated at the international level is growing at an impressive pace. Third, given the growing number of actors and the issues they regulate, it becomes more difficult for the State to use military force to protect its own interests. Fourthly, the model of state-building based on the principle of "one nation - one state" is losing its relevance. Transnationalism appeals to the inevitable development of numerous links between various actors at all levels of interaction between nation-states, as a result of which such a concept as political sovereignty loses its original meaning. For example,

economic cooperation between nations significantly reduces the risks of confrontation between states, as governments become dependent on the will and interests of the business elite. It is believed that the provisions of transnationalism duplicate neo-Ottomanism, especially in that part of it that is related to conflict situations. The economic and cultural rapprochement of Turkey and Iraqi Kurdistan, according to the ideas of neo-Ottomanism theorists, reduces the risks of confrontation between the Turkish and Kurdish populations of the region. In general, as some experts state, Turkish neo-Ottomanism and transnationalism conceptualized in the USA complement each other at the regional level.

Thus, the simplified schematicity and unambiguity inherent in the previous era in understanding political processes are giving way to new realities that are more difficult to understand and sometimes unpredictable. The ability not only to recognize emerging transformations in the Middle East and the post-Soviet space, but also to anticipate possible challenges, becomes one of the main tasks of domestic humanitarian knowledge.

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